

On the Construction *fatale peregi* in *CIL VI, 5953 (CLE 1068)**

To José Miguel

The aim of this paper is to put forward a significant observation about the recent correction of *CIL VI, 5953*¹, a *carmen epigraphicum*, proposed by M. Massaro². This correction has resulted in a construction *fatale peregi* with no epigraphic or literary parallels, a construction to be included in the Latin dictionaries. *CIL VI, 5953* contains an eight lined epitaph dedicated to a young man, *Successus*, by his sister *Primigenia*. The first three lines are in prose; the remainder make up a poem formed by two elegiac couplets with some prosodic faults. The text contained in the major editions and compilations, such as *CIL* (see fig. 1) or F. Bücheler's *CLE*, had been transmitted unaltered since it was established in the eighteenth century.

5953 *tabulam marmoream fuisse in monumento supra aediculam muro affixam indicat PIRAN. t. IX.*
Nunc extat in museo Capitolino.

D·M·SVCESSI PRIMIGENIA·SOR
FECIT·FRATRI·BENE·MERENTI
ET·PISSIMO ITER·VII·ANNIS·EGO
IAM FATALE·PEREGI NVNC·RAPI
OR·YENEBRIS·ET·TEGIT·OSSA·LAP
DESINE·SOROR·ME IAM·FLERE
SEPVLCHRO·HOC ETIAM·MVLTI
REGIBVS·ORA TVLIT

Fig. 1. *CIL VI, 5953*

Massaro has rightly corrected the noun *iter*, at the beginning of the poem, in the third line, by the adverb *ter*, given that the stone clearly contains no *-i*. Consequently, the first verse of the *carmen* must be read *ter VII annis ego iam fatale peregi*. Most probably, this mistake was triggered by misinterpreting a stroke,

* This work has been undertaken in the framework of a Spanish research group (PAIDI HUM-156).

¹ Preserved in the *Palazzo Nuovo* of the Capitoline Museum, fixed in the wall of the *Sala delle colombe* (inv. NCE 1941).

² M. MASSARO, *Un "iter" di fantasia. Revisione e commento di CIL VI 5953 / CLE 1068*, in *ZPE* 187, 2013, p. 164-172.

actually a *uirgula*, used to separate the *praescriptum* in prose from the verse³. This *uirgula* was wrongly understood as an *-i* giving as a result the reading of a word *iter* which no one had thus far questioned. As a matter of fact, from a semantic outlook, the sequence *fatale peregi*, at the end of the first hexameter, reflects the “life is a journey” metaphor of which there are close parallels in Classical Latin authors. In the frame of this metaphor, a construction with *peragere* demands a noun such as *tempus*, *aeuum*, *cursum* or *iter*. There are examples of *perago* construed with all these nouns with the meaning ‘to live out / to complete (a period of time)’ or ‘to live out one’s life’⁴:

- Verg., *A.* IV, 653: *et quem dederat cursum Fortuna peregi.*
- Ov., *Met.* XV, 485: *qui postquam senior regnumque aeuumque peregit.*
- Hor., *S. I.* 6, 93-94: *nam si natura iuberet / a certis annis aeuum remeare peractum.*
- Sen., *Epist.* XCIX, 12: *cui ante lassitudinem peractum est iter?*
- Val. Fl. I, 788-789: *et non segne peractum / lucis iter.*

According to these examples, the word *iter* was likely to be read on *CIL* VI, 5953. This would explain why the first editors opted for the *lectio facillior* by reading (or reconstructing) this word, which was perfectly appropriate in the context of the inscription.

In addition, some other examples of similar constructions with *perago* meaning ‘to live’ can also be found both in verse and prose epigraphs:

- *CIL* VI, 38425 (*CLE* 1948): *Hic ego nunc iaceo... peragens tertium et uicensimum annum.*
- *CIL* VIII, 27587 (*CLE* 1869): *annos peregit duos et octoginta.*
- *AE* 1364, 1995: *M(arci) Aurelii Sam[---] iter qui conducens uitam peregit.*

The closest parallel for the *fatale peregi* construction is in *CIL* VI, 25022: *nulum dolorem accepi tui nisi quod fatalem diem celeriter peregisti*⁵. Nonetheless, what we have in *CIL* VI, 5953 is a construction *fatale peregi* without the expected object. This *aporia* can be tackled from two different points of view: either *fatale* is substantivised as the object of *perago*, or *fatale* is used as an adverbial accusative modifying the verb. Massaro stands for the first solution by interpreting this construction as the result of the use of the adjective *fatale* as a noun⁶. This possibility is supported by the *ThLL*, where some instances of *fatale* used as a substantive are mentioned⁷. These instances can be divided in three categories, among which the following passages are significant:

- 1.1. Stat., *Silu.* II, 1, 226: *quae nubes fatale sonet.*
- 1.2. Cic., *Fam.* XII, 13, 1: *fatale nescio quid tuae uirtuti datum.*

³ About this *uirgula* see M. LIMÓN, *On the Recent Correction of CIL VI, 5953*, in *Tyche* 29, 2014, p. 273-274; MASSARO, *Un “iter”* [n. 2], p. 165 also mentions it briefly.

⁴ See *perago* 10, in P. G. W. GLARE, *Oxford Latin Dictionary*, Oxford, 2012².

⁵ I owe this example to one of the anonymous reviewers.

⁶ MASSARO, *Un “iter”* [n. 2] p. 168.

⁷ O. HEY, art. *fatalis*, in *ThLL* VI.1, 1912-1926, col. 334, 81ss.

2. *Fatale* referring to an infinitive clause: *CIL* VI, 22251 (*CLE* 1127): *si pietate aliquem redimi fatale fuisset Marsidia Stabilis prima redempta forem.*

3.1. *Fatale* referring to a sentence: *Ov., Epist.* 4, 63: *hoc quoque fatale est: placuit domus una duabus.*

3.2. With *ut*: *Tac., Ann.* XII, 64: *fatale sibi, ut ... ferret.*

However, all these examples can be refuted since it appears that *fatale* is rather used as an adjective. In the first case, *fatale* is considered by the *OLD*⁸ as an example of adverbial accusative, a subtype of internal accusative whereby the adjective modifies the verb with which it is construed⁹.

In instance 1.2, *fatale* clearly modifies the compound pronominal form *nescio quid* as an adjective. Similar constructions can be found, for example, in *Cic., Fam.* VII, 5, 2: *tanta fuit opportunitas ut illud nescio quid non fortuitum sed diuinum uideretur.* Example number 2 is rather to be understood as a copulative construction in which *fatale* applies to an infinitive complement sentence as an adjective. This construction is the same as in *Hor., Carm.* 3.2.13: *dulce et decorum est pro patria mori*, a well-known example. The third case is slightly confusing, because *fatale* does not apply to the following sentence, as implied in the *ThLL*, but to the pronoun *hoc*. In fact, that sentence is the referent of *hoc*. It is the same case as in *Man.* IV, 118: *hoc quoque fatale est, sic ipsum expendere fatum.* The same construction is to be found with different adjectives in *Sen., Phoen.* 368: *hoc quoque etiamnunc leue est: peperit nocentes.* Finally, instance 3.2 is similar to number 2 but, in the former case, *fatale* applies to a finite sentence instead of to an infinitive.

Then, how should we explain this *fatale peregi* construction? It is quite possible to understand the text without *iter* and still have it maintain its sense. According to the dictionaries, there is an absolute use of *perago* with the sense 'to live'¹⁰ which is documented only once in the classic authors:

Pers. V, 1389-1390: *regustatum digito terebrare salinum / contentus perages, si uiuere cum Ioue tendis.*

This is a poetic employment that may exhibit Greek influence (see intr. *διάγειν* 'to live' = tr. [*βίον, αἰῶνα, χρόνον*] *διάγειν*)¹¹. We also have to bear in mind the possibility of an analogy after the attested use of *ago* and *dego* with the ellipse of *uitam*¹². In this regard, another example of intransitive *perago* on *Vet. Lat.*,

⁸ *fatalis*, 1.b., in GLARE, *Oxford Latin Dictionary* [n. 4].

⁹ Note that the neuter of an adjective is elsewhere used with this verb: *VERG., A.* 6. 50: *nec mortale sonans*. I thank one of the anonymous reviewers for this observation. See also *G.* 3.149: *acerba sonans*.

¹⁰ A. PERI, art. *perago*, in *ThLL* X.1, fasc. VIII, 1994, col. 1178, 56-62.

¹¹ See *διάγω* in H. G. LIDDELL / R. SCOTT / H. S. JONES, *A Greek-English Lexicon*, Oxford, 1940⁹.

¹² O. HEY, art. *ago*, in *ThLL* I, 1900, col. 1401, 51ss. and K. STÖGER, art. *dego*, in V.1, 1910, col. 385, 27 ss. On the example of Persius see also R. A. HARVEY, *A commentary on Persius*, Leiden, 1981, p. 165.

Tit. 3.3 is significant¹³: *seruientes... uoluptatibus uariis in auaritia et inuidia peragentes*. It is to be noticed that *peragentes* translates *διάγοντες* in the Greek original¹⁴ and that it was replaced by *agentes* in the Vulgate and by *gentes* in Theodore of Mopsuestia's commentary¹⁵. As seen above, *perago* can occasionally become intransitive, and as such, it might be determined by a neuter adjective in the accusative which becomes adverbialised, i.e. an internal accusative. In Latin this kind of accusative is typical of pronominal forms¹⁶, but it is also attested with adjectives, especially in poetical texts¹⁷.

In my opinion, the best way to understand *fatale peregi* is by considering *fatale* an internal accusative. If this interpretation is correct, in *CIL* VI, 5953 we have a variant of the [*aeuum, uitam, tempus*] *peragere* construction, halfway between the absolute use of the verb and the expected transitive one, by employing the adjective *fatale* ('ordained by fate'/'according to fate') as a modifier of the verb. Despite its seeming rare, this verse must have been perfectly understandable to a Latin speaker:

Ter VII annis ego iam fatale peregi

"In 21 years I already lived fatefully (i.e. as decreed by fate)"

This is certainly most poetic, although we cannot determine whether it was the result of a conscious literary intention or of an awkward variation of an unknown model, since no exact parallels are known. Positively, this is not a common use of the internal accusative, but it is a more realistic option than the use of *fatale* as a noun, of which there seem to be no examples.

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¹³ Two other late examples are also cited in the *ThLL*: CONC.^S IV.2 p. 103, 36 (*nunc uestrum est ... sic peragere, ut...*) and SACR. Greg. 31 (*fac nos ita peragere, ut tibi placere ualeamus*).

¹⁴ ἐν κακίᾳ καὶ φθόνῳ διάγοντες.

¹⁵ H. B. SWETE (ed.), *Theodori episcopi Mopsuesteni in epistolas B. Pauli commentarii. The Latin version with the Greek fragments*, II, Cambridge, 1882, p. 252.

¹⁶ For the neuter adjectives as internal accusatives see A. ERNOUT / F. THOMAS, *Syntaxe latine*, Paris, 1959², p. 26, §35 ("accusatif de qualification"); H. RUHENBAUER / J. B. HOFMANN, *Lateinische Grammatik*, München, 1995³, § 116.3.a.

¹⁷ "dichterisch auch mit anderen als Quantitätsadjektive" (RUHENBAUER / HOFMANN, *Lateinische Grammatik* [n. 16], p. 132).